

ADJECTIVE WORD GROUP AND ITS DEGREE

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Abstract. *In this article you will be told and analyzed about adjectives and its levels. Information about quality levels is provided.*

Keywords: *adjectives, comparative adjectives, superlative adjectives.*

ГРУППА СЛОВ ПРИЛАГАТЕЛЬНОГО И ЕЕ СТЕПЕНЬ

Аннотация. *В этой статье вам расскажут и проанализируют прилагательные и их уровни. Предоставляется информация об уровнях качества.*

Ключевые слова: *прилагательные, сравнительные прилагательные, прилагательные превосходной степени.*

INTRODUCTION

Adjectives describe or modify—that is, they limit or restrict the meaning of— nouns and pronouns. They may name qualities of all kinds: huge, red, angry, tremendous, unique, rare, etc

An adjective usually comes right before a noun: "a red dress," "fifteen people." When an adjective follows a linking verb such as be or seem, it is called a predicate adjective: "That building is huge," "The workers seem happy." Most adjectives can be used as predicate adjectives, although some are always used before a noun. Similarly, a few adjectives can only be used as predicate adjectives and are never used before a noun.

Some adjectives describe qualities that can exist in different amounts or degrees. To do this, the adjective will either change in form (usually by adding -er or -est) or will be used with words like more, most, very, slightly, etc.: "the older girls," "the longest day of the year," "a very strong feeling," "more expensive than that one." Other adjectives describe qualities that do not vary—"nuclear energy," "a medical doctor"—and do not change form.

COMPERATIVE AND SUPERLATIVE ADJECTIVES

A comparative adjective is an adjective used to compare two people or things. We use comparative adjectives to say that one person or thing demonstrates a high degree of a quality or is a better example of a quality than the other. Words like taller, smarter, and slower are examples of comparative adjectives.

Let's illustrate how we use comparative adjectives with a hypothetical: you have metal blocks in front of you. The left block weighs 10 pounds and the right block weighs 20 pounds. Because the right block weighs more than the left block, we would say that the right block is heavier than the left block. On the other hand, we could also say that the left block is lighter than the right block. We are using comparative adjectives to compare the blocks to each other by indicating which one has a more extreme degree of a certain quality (heaviness or lightness).

A comparative adjective is formed from the positive form of an adjective, which is the form of an adjective you will find if you look it up in our incredible dictionary. The adjectives brave, fast, and cute are adjectives in the positive form, for example. Here are the rules for forming comparatives from a positive form of the adjective.

Most one-syllable adjectives: Add -er to the end. For example, clear becomes clearer. If the adjective ends in -e, just add -r. For example, free becomes freer. If the adjective ends in -y, you sometimes replace the -y with an -i before adding -er. For example, dry becomes drier but shy becomes either shier or shyer.

One-syllable adjectives that end in consonant-vowel-consonant: Double the final consonant before adding -er. For example, big becomes bigger and wet becomes wetter.

Two-syllable adjectives that end in Y: Drop the -y, replace it with an -i, and then add -er. For example, rainy becomes rainier and ugly becomes uglier.

There are a few adjectives that are exceptions to the above rules. For example, the adjectives quiet, narrow, and clever can use either the -er or the more/less forms. However, we never use both forms at the same time. For example you wouldn't say someone is "less cleverer."

Additionally, there are some adjectives that are irregular. These include good, well, bad, far, and old. Their comparative forms are:

- good and well → better

- bad → worse (Note: The word *badder* is sometimes used as a slang or nonstandard comparative form of bad.)

- far → Some style guides may say that *farther* is preferred for physical distance and *further* is preferred for figurative distance. However, these words are often used interchangeably in everyday speech and writing.

- old → Most of the time, *old* behaves as a regular adjective and its comparative form is *older*. However, when discussing the ages of people, the word *elder* is sometimes used as the comparative form of *old* as in *The elder kitten had darker fur than the younger one*. In general, though, *elder* is not as commonly used, and many speakers and writers will use the word *older* even when referring to people.

When we use comparative adjectives in sentences, we often use them together with the word *than* in order to connect the two people or things we are comparing. For example, we say *This soup is hotter than that one* and not *This soup is hotter that one*. It is entirely possible not to use *than* with a comparative adjective, though, as in *This house is big, but the one down the road is even bigger*. The important thing is that you make it clear what exactly you're comparing when using a comparative adjective.

A superlative adjective is an adjective used in comparisons to describe something as being of the highest degree or extreme. We use superlative adjectives when making comparisons of three or more people or things. The words *biggest* and *fastest* are examples of superlative adjectives.

The word superlative has other uses outside of grammar. As an adjective, superlative is used to mean something is the best or highest of its kind, surpasses all others, or is excellent. For example, a superlative cheeseburger would be a cheeseburger that is extremely delicious or is very high quality. Superlative is also used as a noun, which we will explore more later.

To explain how we use superlative adjectives, let's say we have three sticks that measure one foot, two feet, and three feet long. Of these three, the one that is three feet long can be described as the longest stick because it wins the contest of length. At the same time, the one-foot stick is the shortest as it would win a shortness competition.

A superlative adjective is formed from the positive form of an adjective, which is the initial form of an adjective you will find if you look one up in our fantastic dictionary. The adjectives

smart, kind, and slow are adjectives that are in the positive form, for example. The other form—the form between the positive and superlative and marked by –er or more—is known as a comparative adjective. At our entry for an adjective, you will also see noted what an adjective’s comparative and superlative forms are.

Here are the general rules for forming superlatives from a positive form adjective:

Most one-syllable adjectives: Add -est to the end. For example, warm becomes warmest. If the adjective ends in -e, just add -st. For example, vile becomes vilest.

Two-syllable adjectives that end in -er, -le, or -ow: Add -est to the end. For example, narrow becomes narrowest and clever becomes cleverest.

All other adjectives that are two syllables or longer: Add the word most or least to the positive form. For example, energetic becomes most or least energetic and unbelievable becomes most or least unbelievable.

Note, though, that some adjectives may have more than one acceptable way to form its superlative (e.g., most fun and funnest). When we use superlative adjectives in sentences, we often precede them with the word the. For example, we would say I want to hug the cutest kitten rather than I want to hug cutest kitten or I want to hug a cutest kitten.

However, if we are comparing something to itself, we may not use the word the. For example:

Bears are hungriest when waking up from hibernation.

We also may not use the if we use a possessive adjective or possessive noun instead. For example:

This essay was my longest one yet.

Out of all of her paintings, I think this one is Diana’s best work.

CONCLUSION

In this article, you will learn about the adjective word group and its degree. Adjective word group is one of the main categories. It is divided into types and levels. This article provides detailed information on quality levels. Their formation, in a sentence, use, etc.

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